

Einstein's hypothesis is confirmed by the example of the Schwarzschild problem

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To cite this article:

Ricardo Gobato, Victoria Alexandrovna Kuzmicheva, Valery Borisovich Morozov, “Einstein's hypothesis is confirmed by the example of the Schwarzschild problem”, Parana Journal of Science and Education, Vol. 5, No. 1, 2019, pp. 1-6.

Received: November 1, 2018; **Accepted:** December 26, 2018; **Published:** February 1, 2019.

Abstract

The Newtonian gravity law was deduced with a correction for a non-zero density of a gravity field. The new gravity law is virtually almost entirely congruent with the Schwarzschild attraction law in a zone somewhat distant from the Schwarzschild radius. This confirms with great certainty the hypothesis of A. Einstein that the energy of the gravitational field contributes to the gravitational field. In addition, this contribution is of the same order as the contribution of the Schwarzschild solution. This leads to the conclusion that the energy of the gravitational field should play a large role in the general theory of relativity.

Keywords: General Relativity Theory, Gravity field energy density, Newtonian gravity theory, Schwarzschild problem.

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1. Introduction

Newton's law has since been superseded by Albert Einstein's theory of general relativity, but it continues to be used as an excellent approximation of the effects of gravity in most applications. Relativity is required only when there is a need for extreme precision, or when dealing with very strong gravitational fields, such as those found near extremely massive and dense objects, or at very close distances (such as Mercury's orbit around the Sun). [1, 2]

A relativistic relation between energy and mass does not depend on energy nature, i.e. any energy type – whether it would be energy of matter or energy of fields – can be considered as mass. The principle of equivalency of inertial and gravitational masses makes necessary consideration of total energy in a specified volume as a source of a gravity field. Besides, the gravity field would have energy, if rely on the energy conservation law. Together with the other principles of the general relativity theory, this principle was put forward by A. Einstein in his famous paper [3]. Upon that, Einstein made the important notice:

“It can be seen that along with the components of the energy-tensions tensor of a matter T_{ik} as equivalent field sources, also components of a gravity field tensor (namely θ_{ik}) act. Evidently, this requirement is necessary as a gravitational action of a system cannot depend on a physical nature of energy being the field source”. [3]

However, in the course of his search of his gravity field equation in the general relativity theory, Einstein was forced refusing from the energy of a gravity field as a gravity field source. In other words, in the right part of the equation now known as the Einstein's equation, there is the matter energy-momentum tensor including an electromagnetic field but not including a gravitational mass.

It should seem, this fact would make everyone relating with cautiousness to the Einstein's equation solutions. Nevertheless, curiously enough, this historic fact has been little known to a considerable

part of professionals. Worthy of special mention is the notice by L.D. Landau and E.M. Lifshitz in the second volume of their manual ([4], section 95 “Einstein's Equations”):

“The gravitational interaction plays a role only for bodies with a big enough mass (due to the smallness of the gravitation constant). That is why in gravity field researches usually, we have deal with macroscopic bodies”.

Now, the question on the limits to applicability of the Einstein's equation arouse extremely sensitive. That is why it is important to clarify the role of the energy of a gravity field as a source of the field itself.

Using solely the Newtonian gravity theory, let us consider a spherically symmetric problem of finding gravity field and compare it with the Schwarzschild solution.

2. The classical energy density of a gravity field

Calculating the energy density of a gravity field in the Newtonian limit and considering a thin heavy spherical membrane of a mass M . The acceleration of free fall on the membrane surface is equal to

$$g = \frac{GM}{r^2}. \quad (1)$$

Increase the radius by a small value δr . Upon that, the membrane internal volume grew by the value $\delta V = 4\pi r^2 \delta r$. Along with this, at the membrane radius growth, it is necessary to perform a work equal to

$\delta A = -\frac{M^2 G \delta r}{R^2}$. From which the energy density of a gravity field is equal to

$$w = \frac{\delta A}{\delta V} = -\frac{g^2}{4\pi G}.$$

This value differs from the value obtained as the Newtonian limit in the general relativity theory [4].

3. Gravitational field of a point source corrected for the energy of the gravitational field

Now are able evaluating an impact of an addition of mass density – the equivalent energy (3) – on a point mass Newtonian field. In this problem apart from the central mass, the total mass includes an equivalent of the field mass. Then with due account of the correction factor $\sigma(r)$ to the mass M , the Newtonian gravity law can be written as follows:

$$g = -\frac{G(M\sigma)}{r^2}, \quad (2)$$

where m is a function of r . The following value must be considered as the mass density

$$\rho = -\frac{g^2}{4\pi Gc^2}. \quad (3)$$

This allows – based on (1) – evaluating an augment of a gravity field of a mass membrane having a radius r and a thickness δr :

$$M\delta\sigma = \rho\delta V = -\frac{GM^2}{c^2r^2}\sigma^2\delta r.$$

In limit, have the differential equation

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dr} = -\frac{GM}{c^2} \frac{\sigma^2}{r^2}$$

where from find the correction factor σ . Solving an equation with a corresponding integration constant C

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} = 1 - \frac{GM}{c^2r} + C.$$

As a result with the due account of the “weight” of the gravity field, the gravity law acquires the following form:

$$g = -\frac{GM}{r^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{GM}{c^2r}}, \quad (4)$$

This law (at $2GM \ll c^2 r$) coincides virtually with the well-known gravity law following from the Schwarzschild solution:

$$\alpha_S = -\frac{GM}{r^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - 2\frac{GM}{c^2r}}} \approx -\frac{GM}{r^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{GM}{c^2r}}. \quad (5)$$

Figure 1. Graph for comparison of $g(r)$ to equivalence equations (4) and (5).

4. Gravitational field energy and general relativity theory

Classify the resulting decision as a coincidence or just a curious fact is impossible. The connection becomes apparent between Einstein's postulate on the field energy as a field source, on the one hand, and the equations of the general theory of relativity, on the other hand. Now it is surprising that the extremely successful application of the Einstein equation, despite the fact that it contradicts the Einstein postulate.

See a possible way of developing the theory in replacing the Einstein equation by another [5] and on the development of astrophysical and cosmological models against the background of a homogeneous space [6-21].

4.1. Analysis of Figures

The Figure (1) represents the Graph for comparison of $g(r)$ to equivalence equations (4) and (5). The

figure demonstrates asymptotic equality of the obtained solution and the Schwarzschild solution.

The Figure (2) represents the active giant elliptic galaxy M87. Relativistic jet, which is probably accelerated by a gravitational field and dissipates in a gas-dust cloud. Stability over a long period of time is maintained by a gravitational field, which is generated by jet acceleration. (This Hubble Space Telescope photograph shows the jet of matter ejected from M87 at nearly the speed of light, as it stretches 1.5 kpc (5 kly) from the galactic core) [21-23].

5. Discussions (among peers)

5.1 Schwarzschild's solution

The Schwarzschild solution was obtained under the condition of Einstein's emptiness: all components of the Ricci tensor are zero [4].

This is true, but the article solves the classical problem in the Newtonian approximation. Only the Einstein hypothesis about the equivalence of energy as a generator of the gravitational field is used (see Ref. [1]). The only element of the relativistic theory is equality: $E = mc^2$.

The presence of gravitational field energy is contrary to the Einstein equation. On the other hand, the law of conservation of energy dictates the need for the presence of energy in the gravitational field.

5.2 Einstein's equivalency principle

Einstein's equivalency principle is less than a principle. Where is the equivalency between angular acceleration and a gravitational field? [4]

"I did not mean Einstein's "equivalence principle"". Only the equivalence of mass and energy. The word "principle" can to be removed from the text. This will make the text more understandable.

Figure 2. Active giant elliptic galaxy M87. Relativistic jet, which is probably accelerated by a gravitational field and dissipates in a gas-dust cloud. Stability over a long period of time is maintained by a gravitational field, which is generated by jet acceleration. (This Hubble Space Telescope photograph shows the jet of matter ejected from M87 at nearly the speed of light, as it stretches 1.5 kpc (5 kly) from the galactic core) [23, 24].

6. Conclusions

This was not a general relativity check. Understand how true Einstein's hypothesis is about the equality of all types of energy as sources of the gravitational field. The result was unexpected. The gravitational field in the Newtonian limit almost coincided with the Schwarzschild solution.

This suggests that the Einstein hypothesis could lead to a more accurate equation of the gravitational field. The program Implemented by Einstein failed. In the modern general covariant equation of Einstein does not contain the energy of the gravitational field in the right-hand side. The more surprising is the success of the Einstein equation in solving gravitational problems.

Based on what has been said it can assume that the development of general relativity can go along the

path of abandoning the Einstein equation. Some progress has already been made in this direction.

Acknowledgements

To prof. PhD. Bernard Howard Lavenda, for questioning.

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